

Between Marhi and Math: The Temple of Veer Nath at Rato Kot (Sindh, Pakistan)

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If you want to become a yogi
then observe the tradition of the yogis
Forget adab, iklas, sabr, shukur enmity and sorrows,
Inayat says you should spend every moment of your time
buried within yourself,
When you have learned this undertaking,
then you will come nearer to Veer Nath
Miyon Shah Inayat

Introduction

As apparent from the above verse of Sufi poet Miyon Shah Inyat, Veer Nath was an eminent Nath Yogi. He was also the founder of the Veernathi sampraday. Veer Nath Ji Marhi near Umarmkot, once an important centre of Nath Jogis of Rajasthan, Gujarat, Punjab and Sindh, still attracts both ascetics and common people. Veer Nath was a seventeenth-century Nath Jogi. This paper discusses the role played by Veer Nath in converting several people to “Nathism” and his disciples whose “Samadhis” are still sources of solace for the lower Hindu castes.

Before discussing the history associated with the role of Veer Nath and his disciples, it is necessary to first define the terms *marhi* and *math*. The term *marhi* refers to the centre or a monastery of the Naths. The followers of Veer Nath further define the term *marhi* as the centre or place of worship of *grihashtis* or householder Naths whereas the term *math* is used for the *astan* (place of worship) of the Naga Naths. But this explanation is not very convincing as there are *marhis* which were founded by the Kanphatta Jogis. Moreover, the term *math* is also used for the burial place of an ascetic. To avoid sectarian affiliation, I will be using the term *marhi* for the

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monastery of Veer Nath as it is locally called by the people. There are several *marhis* in many districts of Sindh, the prominent of which include: the marhi of Ratan Nath at Taung, the Jogi marhi near Islamkot, the Balakram marhi, the Dwarkanath marhi and the Jumnadas marhi in Shikarpur. A *marhi* serves as the place of worship for the Nath Jogis. The Veer Nath marhi is believed to have been founded by Veer Nath himself early in the seventeenth century. This *marhi* became the main centre for the Nath Jogis of Sindh who spread the teachings of Veer Nath. Over a period of time, this group of Nath Jogis became so powerful that they were even involved in the political decisions of the Sodha Rajputs in settling disputes between the various lineages of the tribe. Veer Nath's followers played a very instrumental role in resolving the family disputes of the Sodha Rajputs of Tharparkar. Their advice was always sought by the Sodhas during times of crisis and war in Tharparkar.

The information presented in this paper comes from interviews that were conducted with the caretaker and the disciples of Veer Nath. Some interviews were also carried out with members of the Charan, Sodha and Maganhar castes of Umarmkot, Kharerio Charan, Chhor, Pabuhar and Densi. Both in-depth and focused interviews were undertaken to acquire knowledge about the history, role and rituals of the Veer Nath sect of Nath Jogis. As well, all of the *samadhis*, shrines, temples and *marhis* that were associated with the Veernathi Sampraday were visited .

Temples and *dhunis* (campfires) of world-renouncers (Nath Jogis, Tyagis, Sannyasis, Baragis, Sadhus, Babas and Udhasis) exist in almost every important town and village of Sindh. At present, very few towns and villages in Sindh boast of such temples, *maths* (also called *matha*) *marhis* and *dhunis* of Hindu and Sikh ascetics. Among such temples, *marhis* and *dhunis*, the *marhi* of Veer Nath at Rato Kot, which is located about 70 km north-east of Umarmkot, is quite prominent.

As discussed earlier, the *marhi* is believed to have been established by Veer Nath himself who came from Haryana in India and first settled in Umarmkot. Veeso Sodho, the then ruler of Rato Kot, took him to his town and built a temple for him and his disciples. After his coming to Rato Kot, the town's name and fame spread far and wide and ascetics came from Rajasthan and other parts of India to enroll themselves as his *chelas* (disciples). Veer Nath traveled extensively to the popular pilgrimage centres of Gujarat, India, Sindh, Balochistan and he even went to

perform some yogic practices at the pilgrimage centre located at Tilla Jogian which belonged to the Jogis of Jhelum, Punjab.

During the rule of the Sodhas, Rato Kot was a flourishing town where a number of temples existed. However, the temple of Veer Nath (the Veer Nath Ji Marhi) was most prominent. Veer Nath belonged to the Nath renunciatory order, with “Nath” being the rubric term that may cover any of loosely-organized associations of the Shaivite renouncers, taking Shiva as their first *Nath* or *guru*. The Naths are masters of Yogic power and, as renouncers, they are celibate ascetics whose tradition must be passed on through recruitment and through guru-disciple transmission (Gold 1992:37). “Nathism” has been recognized by some as a separate strand of popular Indian religions representing, perhaps, an ancient religious tradition alongside “Vaishnavism” and “Shaivism”. However, in more recent times at least, Gorakh Nath has been identified with Shiva and, since the sixteenth century, the Nath tradition (together with Shaivism) has become partially eclipsed in north India by Vaishnava devotion. Nevertheless, the Naths still remain vital today, not only through the texts and legends that they have left behind, but also within the religious communities (Gold and Gold 1984:115). Sen characterizes the Nath cult as “an esoteric yoga cult based on austere self-negation and complete control over the vital, mental and emotional functions (Sen 1960:42). But as Nath teachings spread within popular Hinduism, both their content and mode of transmission changed. From secret instructions imparted by *guru* adept to select disciple, *nath* ideas passed into folklore. There, these teachings are strongly associated with the “perfection of the body” (*kaya sidhhi*) and the quest for immortality (Eliade 1973; Maheshwari 1980). Nath may be simply defined as “Master” and the Naths as “Masters’ (of yogic power)” (Vaudseville 1974:85). Most of the scholars treat the terms *Nath* and *yogi* as interchangeable when dealing with the sect and its teachings (ibid:85-86). Many for the sake of clarity, settle upon one or the other to use when speaking of that tradition. The terms *Nath* and *yogi* are far exhausting the descriptive designation applied to naths. Briggs discusses, “Gorathnathi,” “Darsani,” Kanphatta and Natha- all categorization with identical or overlapping references that at times designate members of the sect(s) with which he is concerned (Briggs 1973:1-2).

There are ten orders of ascetics (popularly known as Dasnamis) namely: Aryana, Asrama, Bharti, Giri, Parvata, Puri, Sarasvati, Sagara, Tirtha and Vana (Ghurye 1953:82). However, some

scholars and oral historians believe that there are more than sixty-five sects of renouncers. Each renouncer adds his adopted name to one of these ten orders depending on the centre in which he was initiated or the teacher who initiated him (Tripathi 1978:42). It was thought that by practising severe austerities, Nath Jogis earn divine blessings and thus themselves become manifestations of divinity.

Veer Nath first settled in Umarnkot and established his *dhuni* (campfire) which is still popularly known as 'Veer Nath Ji dhuni' (the campfire of Veer Nath) where today the *samadhi* of Gunesh Gar, a patron saint of the Rebaris or Raika caste, is located. According to legend, both were renowned ascetics and an interesting religious discourse took place between them. Gunesh Gar overpowered Veer Nath during the religious discourse and Veer Nath had to leave Umarnkot for Rato Kot. Another version of the story is that later on, the Sodhas took him to Rato Kot after which he made Rato Kot his permanent abode. It was Veeso Sodho who facilitated him (Harijan 2005) and is believed to have built the temple for Veer Nath, who died in 1604 A.D. The latter Sodhas also patronised the Nath temple at Rato Kot and repeatedly gave donations for the upkeep of the temple. Rato Kot became a well-known centre of the Nath Jogis and the terms 'Jogis' and 'Naths' are interchangeably used in Tharparkar.

The Nath Jogis in Sindh

The province of Sindh was considered as a stronghold of the Nath Jogis and, as such, there were many sacred places of the Jogis in Sindh. According to Briggs (1982:103-4), the Asapuri at Nagar Thatta, Koteswar and Pir Arre (Aari) were some of the sacred places which were associated with the Nath Jogis. However, Briggs does not mention the other sacred places that belonged to the Naths in Sindh which include the marhi of Ratan Nath at Taung, the temples of Ballpuri and Mangal Gar near Thana Bula Khan, the Dwarkanath marhi at Shikarpur, the temple of Mata at Ganjo Takar, Hyderabad and the temple of Ratan Gar at Kharerio Charan, Umarnkot.

The Naths were mentioned in several historical accounts that were written during the Kalhora (1680-1783) and Talpur Periods (1783-1843). The renowned Sufi, Shah Abdul Latif, who travelled to their religious places with them, mentioned the rituals that they performed there in his poetry. Interestingly, he also discussed several of the renouncers who made pilgrimages to sacred places. The list that he provides in his poems is very long. Shah has devoted two *surs*, Ramkali and Khahori exclusively, to the yogis and there are also some references in other *surs* as

well. Shah used several titles to refer to the yogis. Some of the names refer to the sects and sub-sects of different groups of yogis, while others are adjectives which allude to their characteristics, for example, the term '*dothi*' suggests those who eat *duth* (wild plants), *gunga* and *bora* mean mute and deaf, i.e. the yogis who have voluntarily stopped talking and listening. The titles by which he refers to yogis are: Mahesi, Shivaite, Kanphata, Kancut, Kapar, Babu, Behari, Nanga, Adesi, Mavali, Sabri, Malakuti, Jabaruti, Kapat, Faqir, Khahori, Nuri, Nari, Dothi, Gunga, Bora, Sannyasi, Bhabhutiyya, Khaki, Rawal, Harkes and Gaudariyya (Sayed 1988:119). This list shows the sectarian affiliation of various ascetics. The Naths of the Veernathi sect are also referred to as "Langotiyas /Nagas" by the current caretaker and the followers of Veer Nath.

The Samadhis of Veer Nath and His Disciples at Rato Kot

More than ten *samadhis* exist in Veer Nath's *marhi*. People belonging to the Hindu religion come to pay homage to these ascetics however, the most important *samadhi* is that of Veer Nath after whom the *marhi* is named. He was believed to have extensively travelled to every 'nook and corner' of Sindh to convert other Hindus to Nathism. He even went to Multan and the famous Joghi pilgrimage centre at Tilla Jogian as narrated by his disciples who resided at Rato Kot. There are many of Veer Nath's *dhunis*, *takyas* and *thalas* (platforms) in Upper Sindh, particularly in the districts of Dadu, Jacobabad and Shikarpur, where he visited his disciples. Particular mention should be made of the Dwarkanath *marhi* that is associated with the Kanphata Jogis in Shikarpur where Veer Nath stayed for a longer period of time as compared to other parts of Sindh.

There is also a Veer Nath Temple near Boreri Village in Khairpur Nathan Shah Taluka, Dadu. Veer Nath also spent some time here and established his *dhuni* there. Later on, his disciples erected a temple over his *dhuni*. There is also a *takya* belonging to Veer Nath that is south of the *samadhi* at Ratan Nath, 2 km west of Taung in Thana Bula Khan Tehsil of District Jamshoro. Veer Nath spent considerable time at *Samadhi* of Ratan Nath before visiting Hinglaj. Baba Ratan Nath lived before Veer Nath and he practised austerities in the mountainous regions of Sindh and Balochistan where there are still many places bearing his name. Baba Ratan Nath is also believed to have travelled to Tilla Jogian, Peshawar and Kabul (Afghanistan).

There is also a small shrine of Veer Nath at the temple of Pir Pithoro. The main *thalo* (platform) where he used to halt before setting out to the main pilgrimage centres in Sindh and Balochistan is located in Sabo Village, which is situated 1 km north of Dhoru Naro in District Umarkot. Apart from the *samadhis* of Veer Nath and his disciples, there are also two temples at Veer Nath's marhi.

The first temple belongs to Sheranwali/Durga and the other to Shiva (Fig.1). The temple of Durga is of Veer Nath's time. It is believed to have been built by Veeso Sodho where Veer Nath and his *chelas* used to practise *tapas* or *yog sadhna*. The second temple, which belongs to Shiva, was erected in 1995 by the Sonara community of New Chhor Town. The Sonaras also repaired all of the *samadhis* of the Nath Gurus. They also placed the image of Shambho Nath in the marhi of Veer Nath and the octogonal tomb was then erected above the image of Shambho Nath (Figs 2 & 3).

The four *samadhis* lie under the canopies (Fig.4). The two 'northern' canopies belong to Leel Nath and Shambho Nath. To the south of these are the *samadhis* of Veer Nath and his *chela*, Nirmal Nath (Fig.5)

Veer Nath's *samadhi* was built by the Hindu Sonara community of Umarkot and two *samadhis* under the building crowned by *shikaras* are situated there. The 'eastern' *samadhi* belongs to Veer Nath (as evident from the inscription) and the 'western' one belongs to his second guru, Nirmal Nathji.

Nirmal Nathji

Nirmal Nathji was the first *chela* of Veer Nath. He belonged to Sisodiya Rajputs. After the death of Veer Nath he became the guru of Nath community at Rato Kot. Like his master Veer Nath, he also travelled to famous Nath pilgrimage centres in Kutch, Balochistan and Punjab. He died in 1634 and was succeeded by Peero Nath.

Peero Nathji

Peero Nath was a Kachhwa Rajput who was converted by Veer Nath when the latter visited the Jaipur region in Rajasthan. He was originally a resident of Jaipur, but he left there and accompanied his 'master' to Rato Kot in Sindh. He remained as the Guru of Veernathi Jogis at Rato Kot for fourteen years. He died in 1648 AD and was succeeded by Rupa Nathji.

The temple of Veer Nath

Rupa Nathji

Rupa Nathji was a Waghela Rajput who was converted by Nirmal Nathji. Rupa Nathji (1648-1664) spent much of his time travelling in Tharparkar, Rajasthan and Kutch where he converted many people to 'Nathism'. Rupa Nathji is also believed to have visited the *samadhi* of Baba Ratan Nath at Taung. He died in 1664 AD and was buried at Rato Kot marhi.

Hira Nathji

Hira Nathji belonged to a royal family of the Jareja Rajputs of Bhuj. He is believed to have been converted by Rupa Nathji during the latter's frequent visits to Bhuj and Girnar in Kutch. Hira Nathji also converted many people to 'Nathism'. He died in 1684 AD and was succeeded by Peepa Nathji

Peepa Nathji

Peepa Nathji was also an eminent Nath Jogi who became a disciple of Rupa Nathji when the former visited some villages that belonged to the Solanki Rajputs in Gujarat with Peepa Nathji coming from the Solanki lineage of the Rajputs. After the death of Hira Nathji, he became the Guru of the Naths at Rato Kot. Peepa Nathji made several pilgrimages to Hinglaj in Lasbela. According to a caretaker of the temple of Veer Nath, he also visited the marhi of Ratan Nath at Taung, Sindh. Peepa Nathji died in 1704 AD and was succeeded by Jote Nathji

Jote Nathji

Jote Nathji was a Sisiodiya Rajput who was born into a wealthy family of Mewargam Village in Rajasthan. Once, he was on his way to Hinglaj when he met the disciples of Veer Nath at Thatta. After returning from Hinglaj, Jote Nathji went to the monastery of Veer Nath where he was initiated into the Veernathi sect of 'Nathism'. It is believed that he was initiated into the Veernathi order of 'Nathism' by Hira Nathji. Jote Nathji was a very knowledgeable person and, as such, he was made the Guru of Veernathi Jogis after the death of Peepa Nathji.

Leel Nathji

Leel Nathji was also a Sisiodiya Rajput and he was born in Chitor Gad, Rajasthan. It is believed that he was initiated into the Veernathi sect by Peepa Nathji. He also made pilgrimages to Hinglaj and visited the famous monasteries of the Nath Jogis in Kutch, Punjab and Sindh. Leel Nathji died in 1770 and was succeeded by Sahaj Nathji

. In addition to those referred to above, several other *chelas* of Veer Nath, namely: Shiv Nathji, Utam Nathji, Bakhat Nathji, Gulab Nathji, Sacha Nathji, Surat Nathji, Suraj Nathji, Aughar Nathji, Shambho Nathji and Badal Nathji, spread the ideology and thoughts of their mentor in Sindh, Punjab, Kutch and Rajasthan.

An annual fair is also held at Veer Nath's marhi. On the eve of the festival, the learned and knowledgeable people of the Hindu faith come from far-flung areas to attend the ceremonies and perform the rituals.

On this occasion, the biographies of both Veer Nath and his disciples are narrated by the people, predominantly eulogizing their heroic deeds and *parchas* (miracles). In order to earn the blessings of these renouncers, people belonging to the lower castes of nomadic artisans and gypsies—Dalits (as well as others) swam the temple during the holding of such religious festivals. The prominent Dalits who attend are the Meghwars, Kolis, Bhils, Kabootras, Odhs, Bagris, Karias, Barhas, Gurgulas, Kuchras, Jatias, Gareras, Dabgars, Kalals, Gawariyas, Gandahoras and Paviyas. They sit near the *samadhis* of the renouncers and sing the songs of praises that they have composed themselves. They also visit the *samadhis* of Oghar Nathji, Utam Shiv Nathji and Sacha Nathji in the village of Ranahoo in Khipro Tehsil of District Sanghar as they were also the disciples of Veer Nath who preached the thoughts and ideology of their mentor in every 'nook and corner' of Tharparkar and who had converted many people to the Veernathi sect. These *samadhis* are still greatly venerated by all of the castes of the Hindus. However, the Sodhas of Ranahoo hold these *samdahis* in greater reverence; they have also taken up the task of maintaining the *samadhis* in good order.

Apart from this, the temple of Veer Nath also serves as the main centre for the novice ascetics who appear to be intensely engaged in yogic practices and in creating an ambiance of harmony and tranquility. People hold these novice students of asceticism in very high esteem and they always try to avoid their 'curse'.

Canopies have been erected over the *samadhis* of Guru Leel Nathji and Guru Shambho Nathji. To the south of these canopies are the *samadhis* of Veer Nath and his first *chela* Nirmal Nathji. To the east of these *samadhis* are the temples of Shiva and Durga. To the north and east of the temple of Durga are *samadhis* of many disciples of Veer Nath.

A marhi at Khyali village, in Barmer district of Rajasthan, is also affiliated with Veernathi sect. A few eminent Naths- Sahaj Nathji, Bakhat Nathji, Gulab Nathji, Suraj Nathji, Badal Nathji were buried in the marhi of Khyala, also known as marhi of Sahaj Nathji. the present Guru of the Veernathi sect lives in Khyala monastery .

Conclusion

The marhi of Veer Nath is still the main centre of Kanphata and the Naga Jogis of Sindh. The ears of young ascetics are still pierced by the present Guru, Gorakh Nath, of the Veer Nath marhi. Although this marhi is associated with the Naga Naths, the Kanphata Jogis also affiliate themselves with the marhi of Veer Nath. The young Kanphata Jogis believe that one of the disciples of Shambho Nath namely, Bhoora Nath, pierced his ears and became a Kanphata Jogi. Since then, a number of Kanphata Jogis regularly visit the marhi of Veer Nath. After their initiation into the Veernathi Sampraday, these young ascetics always go on the pilgrimage to Hinglaj Devi. For them, to be a true 'Nath', one has to make a pilgrimage to the shrine of Hinglaj. With this, their renunciation is thus completed, otherwise it remains incomplete. Similarly, the current Guru of the marhi encourages his disciples to make the pilgrimage to Hinglaj as he believes that without the blessing of Devi (Hinglaj), none of his disciples can be true followers of 'Veer Nath'. Due to every Naga Nath of Veer Nath having made the pilgrimage to the shrine of Hinglaj, they (the Gurus) also expect their disciples to continue the exact same tradition.

This marhi is also a source of solace for the people of the lower tribes who visit it regularly in the hope of the fulfillment of their wishes, which they believe will be granted to them by Veer Nath and his disciples.

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Fig.1 Temples of Durga and Shiva at the marhi of Veer Nath at Rato Kot

The temple of Veer Nath

Fig. 2 Canopy of Shambho Nath

Fig. 3 Image of Shambo Nath at the marhi of Veer Nath

Fig. 4 Samadhis of Leel Nath, Shambho Nath, Veer Nath and Nirmal Nath

Fig. 5 Samadhis of Veer Nath (on the left) and Nirmal Nath (on the right)